

Welcome!

Congratulations on becoming an Instructor with The Carpentries! This document will help you get started with teaching Carpentries workshops and answer any questions.

Where Do I Get Started?

I'm glad you asked! Here are a few things we recommend to everyone:

- **[Review the Code of Conduct](#)**: We are dedicated to providing a welcoming and supportive environment for all people. You agree to abide by our Code of Conduct by participating in this community.
- **[Attend a Welcome Session!](#)** Join members of the Core Team and the community to learn about the organisation, ways to engage, and to have your questions answered. These sessions are designed to provide Instructor Onboarding to help new Instructors prepare to teach Carpentries workshops.

How Do I Get Connected?

There are many ways for Instructors to connect and get information. You can sign up for these to stay up to date on communications specific to Instructors.

- **The Carpentries #instructor Slack** ([Join Link](#)) ([Slack Quickstart Guide](#))
- **Instructor Mailing Lists** ([Instructor List](#))
- **Bi-monthly Instructor Meeting** ([Pretix](#))
- **Bi-monthly Instructor Practice Sessions** ([Pretix](#))
- **Instructor Blog** ([Posts](#))
- **AMY** (<https://amy.carpentries.org/>)

Teaching Centrally-Organised Workshops

All Carpentries Lesson Programs ([Data Carpentry](#), [Library Carpentry](#), and [Software Carpentry](#)) offer workshops taught either in person or online by a team of trained Instructors.

As a certified Instructor, you have access to teaching any Carpentries workshops you are comfortable teaching. To see a list of upcoming Centrally-Organised workshops, sign in to [AMY](#) with your GitHub credentials. You can review [these instructions](#) for using AMY and sign up for upcoming teaching opportunities. *If you need help logging in to AMY, please email team@carpentries.org and include your GitHub username.*

As an Instructor, you must create a workshop website using the [template](#) provided. Once connected with the workshop host, the workshop administrator will provide you with the workshop slug to name your workshop website repository.

Teaching Self-Organised Workshops

As a Certified Instructor, you may also [self-organise](#) unlimited Carpentries workshops at no cost to you. Please complete the [self-organised workshop form](#) to notify us of your planned workshop, so we can add it to our website and provide support (e.g., survey result links and AWS instances for Genomics workshops).

You must create the [workshop website](#) before completing the self-organised workshop form. Remember to create a workshop slug in the format of yyyy-mm-dd-site-online. The slug must match this format exactly to be accepted by AMY.

Once the form has been submitted, the Workshop Administrator will add the workshop to the [upcoming workshops](#) webpage and provide the survey links up to one week before the workshop. It is important to understand [how The Carpentries Core Team use the workshop webpage](#) to coordinate workshops.

Checkout

After attending Instructor Training, there are three steps to complete (in any order) before qualifying as a Certified Carpentries Instructor. Briefly, the three steps are:

1. [Attend a Welcome Session](#). A 1-hour onboarding to the Instructor and the global Carpentries community.
2. [Complete a Teaching Demonstration](#). A 1-hour session where trainees demonstrate 5 minutes of participatory instruction and share feedback, with evaluation by a Carpentries Instructor Trainer.
3. [Get Involved!](#) Choose one more step to further your engagement with The Carpentries.

Additional Resources

- [Frequently Asked Questions about Workshop Coordination](#)
- [Checklist for Workshop Planning](#)
- [Welcome Tip Sheet](#)
- [Instructor Handbook](#)
- [Our Community Glossary](#)
- [The Carpentries Website](#)
- [Accessibility Support Request Form](#)
- [Accessibility Tip Sheet](#)
- [Etherpad to Signup for Teaching Demo](#)
- [Self-organised Workshop Request Form](#)

- [Centrally-organised Workshop Request Form](#)
- [Workshop Website Template](#)

Questions

If you have questions, please email our Workshop & Instruction Team at workshops@carpentries.org.

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